

EASY SHOPPING TECHNIQUES AND THEIR ROLE IN CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF THE OPINIONS OF A SAMPLE OF CUSTOMERS OF VIRTUAL STORES IN IRAQ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to shed light on the influence of simple shopping methods on consumer behavior as well as the correlations and interactions between the two aspects. Researchers in their scientific works present the client and its variables. The second method, called an analytical exploratory method, involves conducting an exploratory study after creating a questionnaire with the aim of gathering data and information relevant to the research. The most crucial of these is the primary query: Is there a role and impact for easy shopping on customer behaviors? To address these queries, a hypothesis reflecting the relationships and influences between the two research dimensions was developed. This led to a set of main and sub-hypotheses that were tested using a variety of statistical means for the data gathered. The research came to a number of conclusions using the questionnaire given to (500) customers in the investigated virtual stores, which were represented by ten stores in Iraq. The most significant conclusion revealed the outcomes of description and diagnosis about people's positive opinions for the two dimensions of the study and its variables through the percentages of agreement and high response, with the emergence of a disparity between the two dimensions and between the two variables. An indication of the virtual stores' propensity for diagnosis and familiarity with the study's principles within the one dimension. The hypothetical virtual retailers rely on simple shopping strategies to change customer behavior because they are trying to diagnose the issue from the field side.

Both ideas that are consistent with these conclusions and proposals for more future investigations pertaining to the two components of the current research were offered based on the theoretical and empirical conclusions reached by the research.

The first topic: research methodology

First: the research problem

The environment of business organizations in general and the marketing environment in particular is marked by the rapid changes in the technological and competitive field, so they must have the ability and high potential to respond quickly to meet these changes by responding to these changes and keeping pace with them in a way that contributes to achieving the goals and objectives of the organization and its continued survival in the market of its industry. Since the (Corona) crisis that the world is currently experiencing forced business organizations to operate in a virtual environment that is rapidly evolving and full of challenges, the market—

and as a result of technological advancement and intelligence, e-marketing—has given rise to the topic of easy shopping, which is one of the significant and contemporary topics that has been widely used. The following questions can help to clarify the core issue of the current study, which is how easy shopping influences customer behavior in the examined virtual retailers.

1. How does easy shopping contribute to customer behaviors for the surveyed virtual stores?
2. Does easy shopping affect customer behaviors for the surveyed virtual stores?

Second, the importance of research

The study acquires its importance from the importance of the two dimensions of the study (easy shopping and customer behaviors), its variables and its chosen field, as the link between these two dimensions is in itself a scientific addition worthy of attention and study, and to produce results that achieve the goals set and represented in demonstrating the impact of easy shopping on customer behaviors.

Third: Research objectives

The research has identified a number of goals that it wants to achieve, as follows:

- 1- Recognizing the contribution of easy shopping to customer behavior.
- 2- Recognizing the extent of the relationship between easy shopping variables and customer behaviors.
- 3- Recognizing the impact of easy shopping on customer behavior.

Fourth: Statistical Tools:

The researchers used a set of appropriate statistical tools to test the research hypotheses, which are:

- 1- Frequencies and percentages of descriptive data, such as gender, age, and others.
- 2- Using the ordinal correlation coefficient analysis, in order to identify the nature of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable at the level of significance of 0.05, using the statistical software SPSS VER.26.
- 3- Using simple regression analysis to show the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, and calculating the value of t and f. and compare them with their tabular values.

Fifth: The research community and its sample

The research community consisted of virtual stores in Iraq, which numbered (10) stores, and the selected research sample was for a number of clients of the investigated virtual stores, and the size of the random sample selected was (500) clients, as the electronic questionnaire form was distributed through Google models, and then collected categorize, sort, analyze and reach the desired results.

Sixth: Research limits

1- Spatial boundaries: The spatial boundaries of the study, as there are no spatial boundaries for it, as it was applied hypothetically to a group of virtual stores in Iraq, which are (Al-Rayyan Shopping, Tamata Shopping, Shobini Shopping, Open Market, Urzady Shopping, Juma Shopping, and Shopping Markets, And Fadshi for shopping, Ain Al Fahd for shopping, and Fekkah for shopping.

2- Temporal limits: from 2/14/2022 to 6/14/2022

3- Human limits: The human limits of this study were represented by customers who deal with the surveyed virtual stores.

Seventh: Action Research Scheme

Figure 1:

Source: Prepared by the researchers

Hypothesis

The hypotheses of this research are determined by the following main hypotheses:

- 1- Do the respondents have different opinions about the variables of the study?
- 2- There is a significant correlation between easy shopping and customer behavior at the 0.05 level of significance.
- 3- There is a significant correlation between each of the easy shopping variables and customer behaviors at the 0.05 level of significance.

4- There is a significant effect of easy shopping on customer behavior at the level of significance 0.05.

The second topic: the theoretical framework

First: easy shopping

1. Easy shopping concept

Easy shopping has become an increasingly common staple of life in the twenty-first century and its popularity can be attributed to the fact that convenience is highly valued in our world today, and more and more people are shopping online instead of shopping in stores offline thanks to the Internet (Kaur & Kaur, 2018:6).

Through the transition from traditional e-commerce to modern e-commerce, which relied solely on the use of the Internet, easy shopping is one of the most recent techniques that has an impact on the global trade sector. Additionally, easy shopping has helped customers save time and effort and helped them. In order for a customer to successfully conduct the online purchase process correctly, within a high degree of caution, a customer should become familiar with the nature of the products offered in the market and that shopping through the Internet needs a set of requirements that should be provided (Wijaya, 2022:196).

2. The importance of easy shopping

The online shopping environment has undergone a major transformation and has become the most popular way to shop today. Easy shopping is very popular in all areas of the customer's lifestyle. It helps marketing managers faster and more efficiently by offering a variety of products. In addition, it helps with customer data integration and usability for marketing managers. When analyzing and interpreting the buying behavior of target customers, shopping is the most effective way to provide valuable and important information to customers and their preferences (Alimamy & Gnoth, 2022:1).

3. Easy shopping variants

Easy shopping techniques are considered one of the organizational strategies that are associated with them, and easy shopping decisions may be strategic decisions within the shopping philosophy of virtual stores

The researchers agreed to identify the easy shopping variables, the most important of which are Prakosa&Sumantika, (2021), Shah&Tiwari, (2021)

A- Virtual Reality: The technology of virtual reality began to appear in the fifties of the last century, but it developed and became more common in the late eighties and nineties. Virtual reality environments are based primarily on visual experiences displayed either on a computer screen or through special screens, but may also include auditory stimulation through speakers or headphones. Users can also interact with the virtual environment through different devices such as a keyboard, mouse, or other, and therefore it can be said that virtual reality may be an electronic environment that simulates the real world or the imaginary world and can simulate the senses such as sight and hearing despite the person's presence in the real world. It also uses

computer-generated graphics through video, audio, and image that can produce environments quite different from those in the real world (Johnston & Bailey, 2018:155)

b- Augmented reality: Many people have said that augmented reality is an evolution of virtual reality and they are two technologies that have two different paths and uses for research and development Augmented reality technology integrates digital information with the real environments in which people live Everything is processed and produced in real time This is one of the main differences With virtual reality using artificial environments, augmented reality using the real world and supplementing it with essentially digital information increases the amount of information a person can take from the environment (Fernandez, 2017:3).

C- Time efficiency and flexibility of choice: The traditional methods of offline shopping take longer than online shopping, as the customer does not need to travel to face traffic congestion and search for parking and also stand in line to make the payment, and therefore many customers want to save more Time The customer tends to save time so that they can complete other urgent matters as quickly as possible, and this constitutes a notable positive case for saving time towards the behavioral intent of adopting easy shopping (Swadia, 2018:22).

d- Reducing the cost of product search: With the growth and increase in the number of customers who use the Internet to purchase many products, easy shopping has become an essential feature of prominent business organizations in the global market today. The customer can shop anywhere and anytime with simple and secure payment options in mind. Because customers are still looking for smarter ways to manage their lives in the market and fulfill their desires in terms of quality products offered, fair prices and getting products on time, so easy shopping, the kind that allows customers to buy products directly from the Internet without the cost of going to the market to search Wasting time and increasing the cost of searching for products (Agrawal, 2020:512).

E - The electronic card: The origin of the electronic card dates back to the nineteenth century, as the first payment process was made electronically via the Internet and the user paid for it with his electronic card. By purchasing an electronic card that contains electronic money, and owners of such cards can pay for their purchases directly. Therefore, the Internet economy has occupied a large part in the structure of the global economy, as the individual does not have to carry paper money to meet his various needs. Rather, the total of electronic cards has become the alternative to spend various operations. Anywhere (Altidjani, 2019:8).

Second, customer behavior

1. Concept

Customers are the primary consideration in the marketing process and the target audience for marketing efforts when choosing what to buy. Additionally, knowing how customers behave can help marketers create tactics that are appropriate for their target market and meet their needs. Because all actions made by people to obtain goods for their use, including making purchasing decisions, are included in this behavior, understanding it is crucial for any enterprises that want to survive and expand in uncertain times (Kler & Mitra,2022:713).

Table 1: Concepts of customer behavior according to the opinions of a number of researchers

Content	The researcher, the year, and the page	No
The activities of individuals, groups, and organizations related to the selection, purchase, and use of products and how those products are consumed to satisfy their needs and desires.	(Kotler & Keller,2012:151)	1.
Behavior preceded by psychological aspects and the desire of customers to buy the necessary products and the organizations' quest to develop a strategy that takes into account the psychological factors to meet the needs of customers	(Di Crosta & Di Domenico,2021:1)	2.
It is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, and use goods, services, ideas, or experiences in order to satisfy their needs and desires.	(Bee & Wangke,2022:300)	3.

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the above sources

2. The importance of studying customer behaviors for customers

A- Identifying all the information that helps the customer to improve the selection of the offered products based on their purchasing power, inclinations and tastes, and identifying their needs and desires based on the priorities identified in their financial resources and environmental conditions around them such as family and social customs and traditions (Shanahan & Taylor,2019:58)

b- Assisting the customer in understanding the process of purchasing and consuming the product (Karanovits, 2021:25)

C - Helping the customer to understand the factors that affect his purchasing and consumption behavior that make him buy specific products and that this experience helps build the brand image (Kler & Mitra, 2022:716).

3. Customer behavior variables

A-Suggestions: These are the information related to the organization that customers provide to other customers, family members, friends, or any person who benefits from purchasing from the organization or obtaining service from it, and this information is often more reliable and credible for other customers as a result of the customer's accumulated experience and experience. With the organization (Anaza, 2014:253).

B-Feedback: Feedback allows providing feedback to the organization and the respondent believes that the quality of products can be positively guided by his reactions, which reduces the loss of customers. In addition, providing feedback to customers allows them to interact with workers and makes customer relations close with the organization and in this In this regard, one of the positive outcomes of customer feedback has been proven to be customer loss prevention (Sarioglu, 2020:4).

C-Customer trust: It is the customer’s belief in the organization’s desire, integrity and ability, and that it is the belief that the other party will act responsibly and that the trusting party will fulfill its expectations without taking advantage of its weaknesses and requires all interactions, especially in uncertain environments such as electronic commerce. It is considered important because it is the degree of uncertainty in economic transactions. In the virtual environment is higher than in the traditional environments (Baki, 2020:106).

D-Customer Happiness: It is the “holy grail” of business success in providing products to customers. The goal of every successful business is to maintain a high level of customer satisfaction by providing value to their customers (Adesina & Chinonso, 2015:1)

E-The electronic word of mouth: It is all informal communication directed to customers through Internet-based technology related to the use or characteristics of certain products or their sellers and this includes communication between producers and customers as well as customers themselves (Litvin & Pan, 2018:4)

The third topic: the practical framework

The third axis: describing the research variables, diagnosing them and testing its hypotheses

First: Description and diagnosis of the study sample. Table (2) presents the description and diagnosis of the study sample members, related to the variables (gender, age, educational attainment, and number of years of service), as follows:

Table 2: Frequency distributions and percentages of the study sample

Sex							
Female				Male			
%		No.		%		No.	
%39.6		300		40		200	
Age categories							
And over - 52		Years 51-41		40-30Years		Less than 30	
%		No.		%		No.	
0		0		1.5		7	
11.5		57		87		435	
Academic achievement							
Postgraduate		BA		Technical Diploma		Preparatory and below	
%		No.		%		No.	
2.4		12		33.4		167	
6.8		34		57.4		287	
The number of times you buy from virtual stores							
or more times		times 16-11		times 10-5		less than 5	
17		6		34		455	
%		No.		%		No.	
1		5		1.2		6	
6.8		34		91		455	

Source: Prepared by the two researchers, based on the results of the SPSS analysis.

The table shows that the female category came with a higher percentage than males, as it was 60% out of a total of 300 out of 500, as a number of questionnaires retrieved and valid for analysis, while the percentage of females was 40% out of a total of 200, with regard to age groups, it was found that the age group between (Less than 30 years old was (87%) of the study sample, which is the most age group that formed the study sample, while the least age group appeared in the study sample, which is between (52 and over) years, and it constituted (0%) Of the study sample members, as Table (2) indicates that (57.4%) of the study sample hold a high school diploma or less, which is the highest percentage among the study sample, while the lowest percentage for graduate studies was (2.4%) of the sample members. The study, as it is noted from Table (2) that the number of purchases was (less than 5 times) with a number of 455 and a rate of 91%, which is the highest percentage among the sample members, while (17 and more times) came with a number of 5 and 1%, which is the lowest percentage.

Second: The respondents' attitudes towards indicators of the two dimensions of research

1. Description After easy shopping and diagnosis. Table (3) displays the frequency distributions, percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviations of the easy shopping dimension through the respondents' answers to the special variables represented (virtual reality, augmented reality, time efficiency and flexibility of choice, reducing the cost of product search, electronic card), as the average The overall agreement for the easy shopping dimension is (86.76%), meaning that the majority of the respondents confirm the existence of (adopting) easy shopping, while the individuals whose answers were in the negative direction amounted to (5.48%), while the percentage of individuals who were not They have an opinion or their answer is neutral (7.76%), so the preliminary analysis of the answers of the respondents confirms the role of easy shopping techniques in the purchases of virtual stores, from its arithmetic mean of (4.404) and a standard deviation of (0.959).
2. description of the customer's behavior. Table (4) displays the frequency distributions, percentages, mean, and standard deviations of the customer behaviors dimension through the answers of the respondents, as the total agreement rate for the customer behaviors variable was (85.65%), meaning that the majority of the surveyed individuals confirm the presence of (adopting). Customer behaviors, while the percentage of individuals whose answers were in the negative direction was (5.65%), while the percentage of individuals who did not have an opinion or their answer was neutral was (8.70), so the preliminary analysis of the answers of the respondents confirms the presence of customer behaviors in virtual stores , from its mean of (4,382) and a standard deviation of (0.969).

Table 3: Respondents' attitudes about easy shopping variables

standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		الواقع الافتراضي
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.850	4.630	2.4	12	2.4	12	2.8	14	14.6	73	77.8	389	X1
0.871	4.482	2.4	12	2	10	5	25	26.2	131	64.4	322	X2
0.960	4.384	2.6	13	2.8	14	10.2	51	22.4	112	62	310	X3
0.920	4.472	3	15	2.4	12	4.6	23	24.4	122	65.6	328	X4
1.014	4.316	4	20	2.6	13	8.8	44	27	135	57.6	288	X5
0.923	4.456	2.88		2.44		6.28		22.92		65.48		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		الواقع المعزز
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.951	4.422	3.4	17	1.2	6	9	45	22.6	113	63.8	319	X6
0.955	4.380	3.2	16	2.2	11	8	40	26.6	133	60	300	X7
1.002	4.334	4	20	1.8	9	9.6	48	26	130	58.6	293	X8
1.006	4.350	3.8	19	2.8	14	8	40	25.4	127	60	300	X9
0.964	4.400	4	20	0.8	4	8	40	25.6	128	61.6	308	X10
0.975	4.377	3.68		1.76		8.52		25.24		60.8		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		كفاءة الوقت ومرونة الاختيار
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.869	4.514	3	15	0.8	4	4.8	24	24.6	123	66.8	334	X11
1.033	4.320	4.2	21	3	15	8.2	41	25.8	129	58.8	294	X12
1.017	4.370	4	20	2.4	12	8.8	44	22.2	111	62.6	313	X13
1.015	4.358	4.4	22	1.8	9	8.2	41	24.8	124	60.8	304	X14
0.976	4.368	3.4	17	1.6	8	10.8	54	23.2	116	61	305	X15
0.982	4.386	3.8		1.92		8.16		24.12		62		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		تخفيض تكلفة البحث عن المنتج
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.916	4.494	3.2	16	1.4	7	6	30	21.6	108	67.8	339	X16
0.955	4.396	3.2	16	2.2	11	7.8	39	25.4	127	61.4	307	X17
0.958	4.386	2.8	14	3	15	8.2	41	24.8	124	61.2	306	X18
0.972	4.382	3.2	16	2.4	12	9	45	23.8	119	61.6	308	X19
1.014	4.352	3.8	19	3	15	8.2	41	24.2	121	60.8	304	X20
0.963	4.402	3.24		2.4		7.84		23.96		62.56		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		البطاقة الإلكترونية
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.913	4.456	3.2	16	1.4	7	7.2	36	21.6	108	66.6	333	X21
0.929	4.408	3.4	17	1.4	7	7.2	36	27.6	138	60.4	302	X22
0.980	4.362	4.2	21	3.2	16	9.4	47	25	125	58.2	291	X23
0.991	4.368	3.8	19	1.2	6	7.6	38	22.4	112	65	325	X24
0.962	4.424	3	15	1.8	9	8.6	43	22.6	113	64	320	X25
0.955	4.403	3.52		1.8		8		23.84		62.84		Total
0.959	4.404	5.48				7.76		86.76				General

Table 4: The surveyed attitudes of their opinions from the dimension of customer behaviors

standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		Neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		الترتيب الانقراضي
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.862	4.622	3.2	16	1	5	3.2	16	15.6	78	77	385	X26
0.886	4.454	3.2	16	1.2	6	4	20	30.2	151	61.4	307	X27
0.967	4.356	3	15	1.8	9	11.8	59	23.4	117	60	300	X28
0.965	4.410	3.2	16	2.6	13	7.4	37	23.6	118	63.2	316	X29
0.965	4.362	3.4	17	2	10	8.6	43	27	135	59	295	X30
0.929	4.440	3.2		1.72		7		23.96		64.12		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		الترتيب المعزز
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.985	4.374	3.2	16	2.6	13	9.8	49	22.4	112	62	310	X31
0.973	4.360	3.2	16	2.4	12	9.4	47	25.2	126	59.8	299	X32
1.017	4.318	3.8	19	2.6	13	10.2	51	24.8	124	58.6	293	X33
0.973	4.360	3.6	18	1.8	9	8.8	44	26.6	133	59.2	296	X34
1.008	4.338	3.2	16	3.4	17	10.2	51	22.8	114	60.4	302	X35
0.991	4.350	3.4		2.56		9.68		24.36		60		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		كفاءة الوقت ومرونة الاختيار
		%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.945	4.452	3	15	2	10	8.2	41	20.4	102	66.4	332	X36
0.977	4.344	3.6	18	2	10	8.8	44	27.6	138	58	290	X37
1.033	4.310	3.8	19	3	15	10.8	54	23.2	116	59.2	296	X38
1.034	4.314	4	20	2.8	14	10.2	51	23.8	119	59.2	296	X39
1.026	4.324	3	15	4.4	22	10.4	52	21.6	108	60.6	303	X40
1.003	4.348	3.48		2.84		9.68		23.32		60.68		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		تخفيض تكلفة البحث عن المنتج
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.939	4.456	2.6	13	3	15	7	35	21	105	66.4	332	X41
0.966	4.354	3.4	17	2	10	8.8	44	27.4	137	58.4	292	X42
0.992	4.366	2.8	14	3.4	17	10.6	53	20.8	104	62.4	312	X43
0.957	4.346	3	15	2.2	11	9.8	49	27.2	136	57.8	289	X44
0.989	4.344	3.2	16	3	15	9.4	47	25	125	59.4	297	X45
0.969	4.373	3		2.72		9.12		24.28		60.88		Total
standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Strongly disagree		I do not agree		neutral		I agree		Strongly agree		البطاقة الإلكترونية
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	No.	%	No.	%	No.	
0.913	4.456	2.8	14	1.6	8	7.6	38	23	115	64.8	324	X46
0.929	4.408	3	15	1.6	8	8.2	41	26	130	61.2	306	X47
0.980	4.362	3	15	2.8	14	10	50	23.4	117	60.8	304	X48
0.991	4.368	3.6	18	2.6	13	8	40	25	125	60.8	304	X49
0.962	4.424	3.6	18	2	10	6.4	32	24.6	123	63.6	318	X50
0.955	4.403	3.2		2.12		8.04		24.4		62.24		Total
0.969	4.382	5.65		8.70		85.65		85.65		85.65		General

Third: Testing the research hypotheses

1. Correlation Analysis

a) Analysing the relationship between easy shopping and customer behaviors

Table 5: The value of the correlation between easy shopping and customer behavior

	Correlations	Customer behaviors
Easy shopping	Pearson Correlation	0.936**
	P-Value	0.000
	N	500

Source: Prepared by the two researchers, based on the results of the SPSS analysis.

Based on what was stated in Table (5), the third main hypothesis was not validated and then rejected, which states that there is no significant statistically significant correlation between easy shopping and customer behaviors. We note that there is a direct and significant correlation between the two variables of the study, in terms of the value of the correlation coefficient, which reached (0.936) and the probability value (P-value) amounted to (0.000), which is much less than (0.05). Enhancing the concept of easy shopping whenever the customer behaviors increase for this organization, which enables it to compete in the labor market.

b. Analysis of the relationship between the dimensions of easy shopping and the dimensions of customer behavior

For the purpose of knowing the values of the correlation between the dimensions of the easy shopping variable and the dimensions of the customer behavior variable, the results of Table (6) refer to the values of these relationships.

Table 6: values the correlations between the dimensions of easy shopping and the dimensions of customer behavior

Correlations	Customer behaviors				
	Suggestions	Feed back	Happy customer	Customer confidence	Electronic spoken word
Easy shopping	0.907**	0.899**	0.889**	0.884**	0.891**

Source: Prepared by the two researchers, based on the results of the SPSS analysis.

The data in Table (6) reveal the existence of direct and significant correlations between the dimensions of the easy shopping variable and the dimensions of the customer behavior variable, whether if they are studied within the framework of the relationship of each dimension or variable with the dimension or other variables separately, or if they are studied within the framework of their relationships.

As for the strength of this relationship, it appears, depending on the data of Table (6), that it varies, as the relationship between the easy shopping dimension and the variable of proposals

appeared to be (0.907), which is a direct and significant value at a significant level of (0.000) which is less than the value (0.05), which is the highest. The reason for this is that the suggestions made by the customer and listened to by the virtual stores are a means to retain existing customers and acquire new customers, while the relationship between the easy shopping dimension and the customer confidence variable appeared to be direct and moral as the least correlated, in terms of the same coefficient, which amounted to (0.884).) at the aforementioned level of significance.

As for the last of its value in the aforementioned two values, according to what we mentioned above, the sub-hypothesis is rejected and the third hypothesis is accepted.

Influence relationships

In this paragraph, the focus will be on the nature of the influence relationships mentioned in the study model, as follows:

Analysis of the impact of easy shopping on customer behavior:

This hypothesis states that "there is no significant effect of strategic leadership on customer behaviors. This effect was determined at the level under study, as follows in Table (7):

Table 7: The relationship of influence between easy shopping on customer behavior

explanatory variable	relationship direction	dependent variable	regression coefficient Estimate	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval		R ²	F	P-value
Easy shopping	→	Customer behaviors	0.188	0.072	0.047	0.329	0.877	3538.449	0.000
			0.952	0.016	0.921	0.984			

Source: Prepared by the two researchers, based on the results of the SPSS analysis.

It is clear from the table (7) of the results of the regression analysis that there is a significant effect of easy shopping as an independent variable in the customer's behavior after it is a dependent variable, as the calculated F value amounted to (3,538.449), which is greater than its tabular value of (3.92) at two degrees of freedom (1,488) and at a significant level (0.05). The value of the coefficient of determination was (R²) (87.7%), which means that the explained differences in easy shopping are explained by customer behavior due to the effect of easy shopping, and the rest is due to random variables that cannot be controlled or that are not included in the regression model at all. From following up on the value of the β_1 coefficient of (0.952) and its (T) test, it was found that the calculated (T) value reached (59.485), which is a significant value and greater than its tabular value of (1.645) at the level of significance (0.05), and this result indicates that improving (Easy shopping) as an explanatory dimension that leads to the improvement of customer behavior, after which it is a responsive dimension. Figure (7). According to what we mentioned above, the second main hypothesis is rejected, which states that (there is no influence relationship for easy shopping in customer behavior) and accept the

alternative hypothesis, which states that that (there is an effect of easy shopping on customer behaviors).

Figure 2: Normally distributed data for the proportion of easy shopping combined in all customer behaviors

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS statistical program.

Fifth Axis: Conclusions and Suggestions.

First: the conclusions

1) Easy shopping has become one of the most significant major forms of shopping, in addition to being a global phenomenon because of its benefits for the customer to get what he wants from the products in a hurry while sitting at home without having to leave and look for his needs; by simply entering the virtual store, he can easily find and choose all of his needs and then have it delivered for free.

Through easy shopping, the customer can communicate with virtual stores without any intermediaries, get acquainted with their products directly, and obtain the information he needs about the products at any time and 24 hours a day.

The results of the description and diagnosis showed the advantages of the individuals' opinions of the two dimensions of the study and its variables through the percentages of agreement and the high response with the emergence of a disparity between the two dimensions and its variables within one dimension, an indication of the ability of the virtual stores to diagnose and know the concepts adopted by the study and try to diagnose them through the field side. So, the trusted virtual stores rely on easy shopping techniques to improve customer behavior.

The results of the description and diagnosis of the individuals surveyed with regard to customer behaviors through Arithmetic mean values and response rate revealed that the most important dimensions of customer behaviors in proportion is the proposal dimension, while the dimension of customer happiness turned out to be the least important dimension.

Second: suggestions

The need for virtual stores to share ideas with customers to reach new ideas, making them exceed customer expectations and compete with other virtual stores.

The surveyed virtual stores should enhance their use of easy shopping techniques in line with the rapid developments in technologies and environmental variables and use the latest visual designs for virtual stores in order to attract customers, draw their attention and motivate them with attractiveness to those stores and increase their desire to use them. The marketing men in the virtual stores should focus on the principle of customer happiness and make the shopping process distinct and enjoyable and exceed the expectations of the customer. Virtual stores should seek to retrieve customers who have switched to other stores by contacting them and offering them attractive offers.

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